

Comparative Study on Water Quality Parameters of Estuary Water at Bengre Estuary Mangalore

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Abstract: Water resources are very precious for life but unfortunately it was deteriorating by urbanization, industrialization and agricultural activity. This activity lead to alternation of physical, chemical and biological quality of water. Industrialization and urbanization of coastal areas often decrease in coastal resource and also destruction of natural defense system. Four sampling locations were selected from the study area near industrial outfalls based on physical observations obtained during the preliminary survey: two from the sea side toward the estuary and two from the estuary itself. Four places were identified using GPS. The distance between the sampling locations were measured using tape. The distance of sampling location from the shore was measured using tape. Water samples were collected in 1litre polyethylene cans during summer season in the month of march2023. Collected samples temperature was noted using thermometer during collection and was taken to laboratory for analysis. The physico-chemical characteristics of collected samples were analyzed in the laboratory. Water quality parameters like pH, turbidity, electrical conductivity, acidity, alkalinity, total hardness, calcium, magnesium, chloride, fluoride, iron, nitrate, and sulphate, were analyzed using samples of estuarine water taken from particular locations. These water quality parameters were compared with Indian water quality standards. Graphs were plotted using Microsoft excel. Water samples were analysed based on Indian standards2012. Water quality parameters like TDS, total hardness, calcium and chloride were above acceptable limit in Summer Season. Physico-chemical characteristics like pH, acidity, alkalinity and iron, Nitrate was obtained within the desirable limit during summer season. The Total alkalinity at location 2 and location 3 was at acceptable limit. And at location 1 and location 4 the total alkalinity was above acceptable limit. Sulphate content of water was above acceptable limit during summer season. Presence of coil-form and E-coil was very high during summer season. Comparing the water quality parameters of estuary with Indian standard values the estuary water was more polluted at all the four locations. Estuary water is more polluted near Bengre beach and the pollution source in the nearby area has to be treated to protect the aquatic species and the nature. Keywords: Estuary, Water quality, GPS

1.INTRODUCTION

Estuaries are habitats providing unique ecosystem services that benefit humankind and maintain marine ecosystem health. However, the coastal environment, including the estuary and the ecosystem services these provide, is facing rapid degradation due to increasing pressure and likely changes in the near future. Estuaries are highly dynamic, unique, and diverse ecosystem. We may be able to restore estuarine/ coastal system by lowering human activities to decrease pressures, even though it is difficult to distinguish between natural and human -induced stress (Tseng et al., 2021). Estuaries in the worldwide are being exposed to an increasingly complex suit of environmental perturbations such as nutrient enrichment, organic carbon loading, chemical contaminants, habitat loss and alterations, overfishing, freshwater diversion and introduced species, originating from overpopulation and uncontrolled development in coastal watersheds, as well as human activities in the estuarine embayment themselves (Thasneem et al., 2018). At the same time, demand for water for varied purposes such as residential usage, agriculture, industrial usage, etc has increased. The environmental effects of these changes are directly reflected in the parameters of water quality. Water resources are very precious for life but unfortunately it was deteriorating by urbanization, industrialization and agricultural activity. This activity lead to alternation of physical, chemical and biological quality of water. Industrialization and urbanization of coastal areas often decrease in coastal resource and also destruction of natural defense system (Zhao et al., 2011). Agricultural wastes, industrial effluents and urban activities is considered to be the primary source for increasing nutrient load in coastal environment (Kucuksezgin, 2006). Although many studies have been undertaken to evaluate the water quality of Indian estuaries, no scientific studies have hitherto been carried out on the water quality of estuarine and adjoining coastal regions of Bengre estuary. The present study aims to get an insight in to the hydrograph of this estuary

2.MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Location of sample collection points in Gurupura Bengre Estuary using GPS. 2. Collection of water sample in summer seasons from located points. 3. Analysis of physico-chemical parameters of collected estuary water samples for seasons. 4. Comparing the estuary water quality parameters with Indian Standards limits. Study Area Bengre beach is a small sandy island which is located 15.7km away from Mangalore city. It is situated at Banger's conclusion. The region of the Google Earth image is depicted in figure 1. The methodology flow chart is depicted in figure2. Water Sampling locations are as shown in figure3. Table 1 shows the longitude and latitudes of water sampling locations. Four sampling locations were selected from the study area near industrial outfalls based on physical observations obtained during the preliminary survey: two from the sea side

toward the estuary and two from the estuary itself. Four places were identified using GPS. The distance between the sampling locations were measured using tape. The distance of sampling location from the shore was measured using tape. Water samples were collected in 1litre polyethylene cans during summer season in the month of march2023. Collected samples temperature was noted using thermometer during collection and was taken to laboratory for analysis. The physico-chemical characteristics of collected samples were analyzed in the laboratory. Water quality parameters like pH, turbidity, electrical conductivity, acidity, alkalinity, total hardness, calcium, magnesium, chloride, fluoride, iron, nitrate, and sulphate, were analyzed using samples of estuarine water taken from particular locations. These water quality parameters were compared with Indian water quality standards. Graphs were plotted using Microsoft excel.

Figure.1 Study area of Google earth image

Figure.2 Methodology Flow chart

Figure.3 Water sampling locations (S1, S2, S3&S4)

Table 1: Longitude and Latitude values of sampling location

Location	Longitude	Latitude	Distance from the shore	Distance between location
S1	74.827038°	12.847642°	11m	100m
S2	74.827901°	12.847236°	12m	100m
S3	74.828632°	12.846526°	10m	100m
S4	74.829061°	12.846761°	9m	100m

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Physico-Chemical Characteristics

Water samples were analysed based on Indian standards2012. The physicochemical characteristics of location 1,2,3 and 4 is as shown in table 1 and 2. The Physico-chemical characteristics of all four locations during summer season are as shown Bar graphs given in figure 4,5,6,7 and 8.

Table 2: Physicochemical Characteristics of location S1 and S2

SI NO	CHARACTERISTICS	UNITS	ACCEPTABLE LIMITS	RESULTS
1	Color	CU	5	BDL
2	Odour	–	Agreeable	Agreeable
3	Turbidity	NTU	1	2.57
4	pH (25°)	–	6.5 to 8.5	7.92
5	Total Alkalinity (as Ca CO ₃)	mg/liter	200	240.00
6	Total Dissolved Solids(TDS 180°)	mg/liter	500	46390.00
7	Total Hardness (as Ca CO ₃)	mg/liter	200	6060.00
8	Calcium (as Ca)	mg/liter	75	663.87
9	Magnesium(as Mg)	mg/liter	30	107.22
10	Chloride (as Cl)	mg/liter	250	16615.00
11	Taste	–	Agreeable	Agreeable
12	Acidity	mg/liter	–	40.00
13	Sulphate(as SO ₄)	mg/liter	200	346.00
14	Fluoride(as F)	mg/liter	1	BDL
15	Iron(Fe)	mg/liter	1	BDL
16	Nitrate(NO ₃)	mg/liter	45	5.40
17	Residual Chlorine	mg/liter	0.2	–
18	Electrical Conductivity at 25°C	mhoms/cm	–	53320.00
19	Total colifrom	CF/100ml	Nil	187
20	E.Coli	CF/100ml	Nil	97

SI NO	CHARACTERISTICS	UNITS	ACCEPTABLE LIMITS	RESULTS
1	Color	CU	5	BDL
2	Odour	–	Agreeable	Agreeable
3	Turbidity	NTU	1	1.49
4	pH (25°)	–	6.5 to 8.5	8.06
5	Total Alkalinity (as Ca CO ₃)	mg/liter	200	140.00
6	Total Dissolved Solids(TDS 180°)	mg/liter	500	46960.00
7	Total Hardness (as Ca CO ₃)	mg/liter	200	6363.00
8	Calcium (as Ca)	mg/liter	75	582.90
9	Magnesium(as Mg)	mg/liter	30	117.06
10	Chloride (as Cl)	mg/liter	250	3517.04
11	Taste	–	Agreeable	Agreeable
12	Acidity	mg/liter	–	60.00
13	Sulphate(as SO ₄)	mg/liter	200	346.80
14	Fluoride(as F)	mg/liter	1	BDL
15	Iron(Fe)	mg/liter	1	BDL
16	Nitrate(NO ₃)	mg/liter	45	2.71
17	Residual Chlorine	mg/liter	0.2	–
18	Electrical Conductivity at 25°C	mhoms/cm	–	53610.00
19	Total colifrom	CF/100ml	Nil	135
20	E.Coli	CF/100ml	Nil	55

Table 2: Physicochemical Characteristics of location S3 and S4

SI NO	CHARACTERISTICS	UNITS	ACCEPTABLE LIMITS	RESULTS
1	Color	CU	5	BDL
2	Odour	–	agreeable	Agreeable
3	Turbidity	NTU	1	1.00
4	pH (25°)	–	6.5 to 8.5	8.05
5	Total Alkalinity (as Ca CO ₃)	mg/liter	200	200.00
6	Total Dissolved Solids(TDS 180°)	mg/liter	500	47310.00
7	Total Hardness (as Ca CO ₃)	mg/liter	200	6585.20
8	Calcium (as Ca)	mg/liter	75	696.20
9	Magnesium(as Mg)	mg/liter	30	118.04
10	Chloride (as Cl)	mg/liter	250	3575.79
11	Taste	–	Agreeable	Agreeable
12	Acidity	mg/liter	–	60.00
13	Sulphate(as SO ₄)	mg/liter	200	602.30
14	Fluoride(as F)	mg/liter	1	BDL
15	Iron(Fe)	mg/liter	1	BDL
16	Nitrate(NO ₃)	mg/liter	45	2.69
17	Residual Chlorine	mg/liter	0.2	–
18	Electrical Conductivity at 25°C	mhoms/cm	–	53800.00
19	Total colifrom	CF/100ml	Nil	194
20	E.Coli	CF/100ml	Nil	150

SI NO	CHARACTERISTICS	UNITS	ACCEPTABLE LIMITS	RESULTS
1	Color	CU	5	BDL
2	Odour	–	Agreeable	Agreeable
3	Turbidity	NTU	1	2.13
4	pH (25°)	–	6.5 to 8.5	7.87
5	Total Alkalinity (as Ca CO ₃)	mg/liter	200	920.00
6	Total Dissolved Solids(TDS 180°)	mg/liter	500	47300.00
7	Total Hardness (as Ca CO ₃)	mg/liter	200	6645.80
8	Calcium (as Ca)	mg/liter	75	712.40
9	Magnesium(as Mg)	mg/liter	30	118.54
10	Chloride (as Cl)	mg/liter	250	3459.19
11	Taste	–	Agreeable	Agreeable
12	Acidity	mg/liter	–	80.00
13	Sulphate(as SO ₄)	mg/liter	200	319.30
14	Fluoride(as F)	mg/liter	1	BDL
15	Iron(Fe)	mg/liter	1	BDL
16	Nitrate(NO ₃)	mg/liter	45	5.29
17	Residual Chlorine	mg/liter	0.2	–
18	Electrical Conductivity at 25°C	mhoms/cm	–	53990.00
19	Total colifrom	CF/100ml	Nil	201
20	E.Coli	CF/100ml	Nil	110

In Figure 4a, it shows the variation of pH (6.5 to 8.5) content in all four locations S1, S2, S3, S4. where pH content is below the acceptable limit while compared to ISA value. In figure 4b it shows the variation of turbidity content, while comparing it with Indian standard value the turbidity content in the location S1, S2, S4, is very high and in the location S3 turbidity content is within acceptable limit.

Figure 4a&b: pH and Turbidity

In the Figure 5a it shows the variation of total alkalinity content in location S1, S2, S3, and S4. While comparing it with Indian standers value the total alkalinity content is very high at S1, S4 and at the location S2, S3 total alkalinity content are within the acceptable limit. Where as in the Figure5b it shows the variation of TDS (total dissolved solids) content in the S1, S2, S3, S4. while comparing it with Indian Standard values in all the four location S1, S2, S3, S4 the TDS content is very high.

Figure 5a&b: Total Alkalinity and TDS

In the Figure6a It shows that the variation of total Hardness content is very high at all the location S1, S2, S3, S4, while comparing with Indian Standard value. In the Figure 6b it shows the variation of calcium content in the location S1, S2, S3, S4. and while comparing it with ISA values, the calcium content is very high at location S1, S2, S3, S4.

Figure 6a&b: Total Hardness and Calcium

In figure 7a it shows the variation of magnesium content, while comparing it with Indian standard value the magnesium content in the location S1, S2, S3, S4, is very high. In Figure 7b the chloride content is very high at the location S1, S2, S3,

S4. In Figure8a shows the acidity content of water sample in s1,s2,s3 and s4 locations which are within ISA standards. In figure 8b shows the Sulphate content is very high at the location S1, S2, S3, S4 as compared to Indian standard value.

Figure 7a&b: Total Hardness and Calcium

Figure 8a&b: Acidity and Sulphate

In the Figure9a & b It shows that the Nitrate content and Electrical conductivity which are below the acceptable limit at all the four location S1, S2, S3, S4 compared to ISA value.

Figure 8a&b: Nitrate and Electrical Conductivity

In Figure10a we have observed that there is a presence of Total Coliform content is very high at the location S1, S2, S3, S4. In Figure we have observed that there is a presence of the E.Coli content is very high at the location S1, S2, S3, S4.

Figure 10a&b: Nitrate and Electrical Conductivity

4.CONCLUSION

1. Water quality parameters like TDS, total hardness, calcium and chloride were above acceptable limit in Summer Season.
2. Physico-chemical characteristics like pH, acidity, alkalinity and iron, Nitrate was obtained within the desirable limit during summer season.
3. The Total alkalinity at location 2 and location 3 was at acceptable limit. And at location 1 and location 4 the total alkalinity was above acceptable limit.
4. Sulphate content of water was above acceptable limit during summer season.
5. Presence of coil-form and E-coil was very high during summer season.
6. Comparing the water quality parameters of estuary with Indian standard values the estuary water was more polluted at all the four locations.
7. Estuary water is more polluted near Bengre beach and the pollution source in the nearby area has to be treated to protect the aquatic species and the nature

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